

TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7295396>

Abstract. *The article deals with the types and forms of assessing the level of communicative language competence at different stages of learning Russian as a foreign language.*

Keywords: *Russian language, method, foreign language, competence, stage.*

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ИНОСТРАННОГО

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются виды и формы оценки уровня коммуникативно-языковой компетенции на разных этапах изучения русского языка как иностранного.*

Ключевые слова: *русский язык, метод, иностранный язык, компетенция, этап.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL) provides for the presence of two mandatory components: the formation of foreign language (communicative) competence and the diagnosis of the level of its formation (control of knowledge, skills and abilities of students). The aim of the course in Russian as a foreign language is to develop a high level of communicative language competence in all types of speech activity: reading, speaking, writing and listening.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As part of the study of Russian as a foreign language, students must have the following knowledge, skills and abilities:

Students must know [1]:

- lexical minimum in the amount necessary for communication in situations of everyday and educational and professional activities;
- grammatical minimum, including the main morphological categories, methods of word formation and grammatical structures characteristic of oral and written speech;
- linguistic means and structural and semantic features of texts of different functional and semantic types;
- culture and traditions of the country of the language being studied, rules of speech etiquette;
- main sources of information in Russian (vocabularies, periodicals, Internet resources)

Be able to [2]:

- maintain oral speech contacts in Russian in the field of everyday, educational and professional communication;
- read texts on a wide and narrow profile of the specialty in order to obtain information;
- abstract and annotate Russian-language texts of a general scientific and military-applied nature;
- use language means and speech norms depending on the content, goals, objectives, addressee, form and conditions of communication;
- conduct a conversation-dialogue of a general and professional nature in Russian, using the rules of speech etiquette;

- make a prepared presentation (report) on the topics studied;
- fill in questionnaires, compose private and business letters, (auto)biography, resume;
- use modern sources of information in Russian for self-education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In connection with the foregoing, it can be argued that the process of studying the discipline is aimed at developing communicative competence among foreign military personnel, which allows them to use the Russian language as a means of sociocultural, educational and professional communication.

As rightly pointed out by Efremova NF, Kazanovich VG, when creating a fund of appraisal funds, it is necessary to take into account a number of factors [3]:

- didactic-dialectical relationship between the results of education and competencies;
- content of educational programs;
- it is necessary to provide for an assessment of the ability for creative activity that contributes to the preparation of the student;
 - when assessing the level of formation of students' competencies, conditions should be created for maximum approximation to future professional practice;
 - in addition to individual assessments, group and mutual assessments should be used;
 - based on the results of the assessment, an analysis of achievements should be carried out, emphasizing both positive and negative individual and group results, indicating ways for further development

Intermediate certification in Russian as a foreign language is carried out in order to determine the degree of achievement of educational goals in sections of the discipline and is carried out in the form of tests and tests (tests with assessment). as well as writing skills and abilities Test (credit with assessment) serves as a form of testing the assimilation of the material of practical classes and tasks of an extracurricular workshop in Russian as a foreign language. At the same time, skills and abilities in reading, listening and speaking are controlled

The final control consists in objectively identifying the learning outcomes of Russian as a foreign language, which make it possible to determine the degree of compliance of the actual learning outcomes with those planned in the program. The main forms of the final control are exams, which, in turn, can be conducted using various methods (final written work, testing, oral individual survey)

An exam in Russian as a foreign language is held at the end of the study of this discipline in order to check and assess the level of knowledge gained by students, the ability to apply them in solving practical problems, as well as the completeness and level of mastery of practical skills and mastery all types of speech activity in the scope of the requirements of the curriculum.

The most important features of the tests are [4]:

- saving the teacher's time (time consumption is two to three times less than with oral control);
 - the ability to put all trainees in the same conditions;
 - the possibility of developing variants of questions equivalent in difficulty;
 - the ability to objectively evaluate the answers in the absence of the teacher's help;
 - the ability to check the validity of the assessment;
 - reduction of the subjective approach to assessing the student's training, due to his individual characteristics.

In the subtests for writing, reading, listening and speaking, the following forms of test items should be used:

- 1) tasks of an open form;
- 2) assignments for compliance;
- 3) tasks to establish the correct sequence;
- 4) compiling your own statement

There are a number of general requirements for test items [5]:

— each task has its own serial number, established according to an objective assessment of the difficulty of the task and the chosen testing strategy;

- the task is formulated in the logical form of a statement, which becomes true or false depending on the student's answer;

— the correct answer is attached to the developed task;

— for each task, an evaluation rule is given that allows interpreting the student's answer as correct or incorrect.

CONCLUSION

From the foregoing, it follows that the diagnosis of language knowledge, speech skills and abilities in the classroom in Russian as a foreign language should be objective, reliable and understandable for both the teacher and students.

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